

Quantum Heat Transport

Ryan Jamie Buchanan and Lorenzo Rafael Florés

July 24, 2024

The classical heat equation reads:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = q\Delta u \quad (0.1)$$

where

$$\Delta u = \left(\hat{x}_i \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \hat{y}_j \frac{\partial}{\partial y} + \hat{z}_k \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right)^2 u \quad (0.2)$$

Notice that we are free to decompose u as follows:

$$u = \frac{u_i + u_j + u_k}{\log(k - (i + j))} \quad (0.3)$$

For two interacting bodies, a_n and b_m , we have:

$$a_n \boxtimes b_m = f(a_n) \bigotimes_{n+m}^{\infty} g(b_m) \quad (0.4)$$

where

$$\left(f(a_n) = e^{2n\pi i\theta} a_n + e^{2(n-1)\pi \frac{i}{2}\theta} a_{n-1} + \dots + e^0 a_0 \right) \sim \left(g(b) = e^{2^p n\pi i\theta} a_n + e^{(2(n-1))^p \pi \frac{i}{2^p}\theta} a_{n-1} + \dots + e^0 a_0 \right) \quad (0.5)$$

where the equivalence is given by taking $\log_p g(b)$, and where $p = 2^n \pi a$, where a is the intrinsic angular momentum (spin) of the interacting body. The interaction between the bodies is sufficient to transfer thermal energy via a Feynman-Kac type process. The generalized form of this phenomenon reads:

$$T(A) \pm T(B) = \int_{\mathbb{E}} \frac{\partial e^{q\Delta u}}{\partial t} |\Psi(\hat{p})(t')\rangle \quad (0.6)$$

which is given in terms of half-densities on a topos.

1 Transfer of Heat in a Two Particle Setup

Let $\vec{a} = \Delta\alpha$ and $\vec{b} = \Delta\beta = -(\Delta\alpha)$. We have, due to Kapranov, Soibelman, and Soukhanov, the iterated transport equation:

$$\mathfrak{T} = n(k\varepsilon\vec{a} + (k - \varepsilon^2)\varepsilon\vec{a} + \dots + (k - \varepsilon^\infty)\varepsilon\vec{a}) + m(k\varepsilon\vec{b} + (k - \varepsilon^2)\varepsilon\vec{b} + \dots + (k - \varepsilon^\infty)\varepsilon\vec{b}) \quad (1.1)$$

$$= n \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \vec{a} k^i \varepsilon - \varepsilon^{i+3} \vec{a} + m \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \vec{b} k^i \varepsilon - \varepsilon^{i+3} \vec{b} \quad (1.2)$$

$$= (n - m) \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \vec{a} k^i \varepsilon - \varepsilon^{i+3} \vec{a} = \mathfrak{h} \quad (1.3)$$

And, whence $\mathfrak{h}$ is not equal to zero, we observe a transfer of heat. Refer to the left-hand side of equation (1.2) as $\mathfrak{h}(a)$ and the right-hand side as $\mathfrak{h}(b)$. We have, for two bodies:

$$\delta t = \left(\pm \frac{\mathfrak{h}(a) - |\mathfrak{h}(b)|}{2} \right) \quad (1.4)$$

where $\delta(t)$ is the average change in temperature, and $|\mathfrak{h}(b)|$ is the magnitude of $\vec{b}$.

A References

- [1] M. Kapranov, et al., *Perverse schobers and the Algebra of the Infrared*, (2020)
- [2] N.A. Watson, *Introduction to Heat Potential Theory*, (2012)
- [3] M.E. Taylor, *Brownian Motion and Potential Theory*, (1996)